

REINFORCING

Responsible tErritories and Institutions eNable and Foster Open
Research and inClusive Innovation for traNsitions Governance

D2.1 – REINFORCING Community Engagement Roadmap

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Document author/s: [Angela Simone - FGB, Cecilia Gaballo – FGB, Carmen Fenollosa – SD, Anna Pellizzone - FGB]

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The REINFORCING Community Engagement Roadmap is Deliverable 2.1 (D2.1) from the coordination and support action (CSA) REINFORCING Project – Grant Agreement (GA) no. 101094435.

This deliverable introduces the first version of the Community Engagement Roadmap, which includes an overview of the strategy to engage the ORRI community at large to interact with during the duration of the project and a rough timeline of the activation of the different actions.

Engagement activities are at the very centre of the project since they will be essential for the refinement of services and tools to be developed by the REINFORCING consortium and to collect needs from specific sub-communities to define the call texts of the REINFORCING cascading grants. The roadmap will also provide ethical measures to be addressed in the planned community engagement activities (e.g. informed consent) to ensure they comply with the highest standards.

This document is a living document; it reflects the current state of the art of the REINFORCING project. Throughout the project (M20, M32, and M44), there will be checkpoints to assess its effectiveness and identify areas for improvement and updating.

1. PROJECT BACKGROUND

REINFORCING supports organizations and institutions in Europe in transitioning to a new paradigm where responsibility and openness drive research and innovation processes.

In the current situation, the green and digital transitions have become an urgency that can no longer wait. The twin transition, as they have come to be known, will bring enormous benefits but also undesired externalities. Making it fair and inclusive is, therefore, key. To succeed, institutions and territories need to shift to more open and transparent R&I practices in which all actors share responsibility for developing services and products that are acceptable, sustainable, and bring social satisfaction.

The Open and Responsible Research and Innovation (ORRI) approach promotes collaborative efforts. From sharing research outputs as early as possible to engaging citizens in co-creation processes, R&I should be open to the whole society.

Implementing Open and Responsible R&I can seem a daunting task. However, over the past decade, many resources and tools have been created, but an effort to systematize, curate, and create a single entry point is still missing. REINFORCING is this much-needed European central hub for Open and Responsible R&I. The project's platform is the entry point to knowledge, training, ORRI skills match-making, and capacity building for organizations interested in starting or continuing their journey to create an inclusive R&I ecosystem. Furthermore, the project brokers unique networking opportunities for organizations, institutions and territories interested in becoming part of the European ecosystem that is transforming the R&I system by bringing it closer to society and societal needs.

To support this change, REINFORCING has ring-fenced funding for 96 grants - between 20,000 and 60,000 euros- to invite institutions from around Europe to develop projects aiming at implementing new modes of doing R&I that drive more just transitions. The project will launch 7 open calls for cascading grants to help territories and organizations experimenting with ORRI for the first time (ORRI Incubator Open Calls) or to boost those scaling up their ORRI activities (ORRI Booster Open Calls).

2. COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

Community engagement, starting from the development of Communities of Practice (CoP), is increasingly encouraged by organizations such as the European Commission¹ as bringing people with “different knowledge perspectives together and can strengthen their capacity to work and learn creatively together while harnessing the collective intelligence” to deliver integrated work and “overcome silo mentalities”. Regardless of the different approaches and levels of participation, what is undoubtedly true is that communities of practice and actions stimulate cross-organisational collaboration, knowledge sharing and valorisation and have the potential to cut across sector-based divides and to serve as motivational anchors for curiosity and engagement.

As described in Webber (2016)², community engagement has the capability to value explicit and tacit knowledge. It builds bridges among disciplines, stakeholder groups, and organizations, accelerating and improving collective performance in a way that is more than the sum of its parts.

2.1 COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT STRATEGY

As outlined by the Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement (CSCCE) Community Participation Model³, four modes of engagement can occur *within a community* (convey/consume, contribute, collaborate, and co-create). One mode can occur *both inside and outside the community* (champion).

Across these modes, information flow changes, moving from *transmissive*, in which the goal is to transmit information, to *transactional*, in which there is an exchange of information, to *transformational*, in which information is created and applied (see Figure 1).

¹ European Commission, Joint Research Centre, Williquet, F., Szkola, S., Catana, C. et al., *The communities of practice playbook – A playbook to collectively run and develop communities of practice*, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/443810>

² Webber, Emily, *Building Successful Communities of Practice: Discover How Connecting People Makes Better Organisations*, Tacit, 2016.

³ Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement. (2020) [The CSCCE Community Participation Model – A framework for member engagement and information flow in STEM communities](#). Woodley and Pratt doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3997802

Figure 1: The CSCCE Community Participation Model (Adapted from "The CSCCE Community Participation Model – A framework for member engagement and information flow in STEM communities")

Varying in terms of interactions, goals, activities and power balances, the four modes of engagement can coexist and integrate themselves, as described in Table 1 (below). Depending on the scope, the tools available, and the actors involved, one mode can be preferred to another, determining different levels of engagement.

Table 1: The CSCCE Community Participation Model (Adapted from "The CSCCE Community Participation Model – A framework for member engagement and information flow in STEM communities")

Model	Convey/Consume	Contribute	Collaborate	Co-create
Interaction	One to many	Crowdsourced	Cooperative	Community-led
Community Management Goal	Inform and inspire	Obtain feedback, skills, or information	Gather resources, including knowledge, to achieve a common goal	Create something new together
Community Activities	Read, watch, listen	Comment, vote, like tag	Discussion, knowledge exchange, production	Integration and synthesis, multi-directional learning, co-production
Power Balance	Organization as expert	Organization as convenor	Scaffolded cooperation	Mutual sharing and learning (near) equity
Slogan	Here's something interesting	Give us some feedback	How can we work together?	What shall we do next...?

Whilst there is a diversity of collaboration systems - such as knowledge centres, communities of practice and networks for cooperation - different modes and levels of participation can coexist in the same community.

2.2 COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT OPERATIONAL MODEL AND TOOLS

A community is a complex system composed of multiple levels of interaction among people engaged at different levels. For this reason, a set of actions needs to be considered when setting up a community operational model, which is clearly outlined in the Community of Practice Playbook of the JRC⁴ - European Commission.

Vision, which is essential to respond to the mission of the community, defining its identity, general purpose and specific objectives;

Governance, which should be based on a stakeholder mapping exercise, defining rules, procedures and practices to respond to community needs;

Leadership is about identifying and seeking a core group and stakeholder leaders in the community ecosystem that take the initiative, bring people together and take responsibility (which is outlined as a key factor for success)

Convening is the art of gathering community participants and engaging them in meaningful conversations and actions. This aspect of community engagement benefits from a risk-free and inclusive environment, adequate communication and boundary-spanning activities linking the community with external sources of knowledge.

Collaboration and cooperation in support of a shared vision to co-create a shared outcome based on shared goals and purposes. Cooperation happens when members and other actors strategically work separately to accomplish their tasks and need collaboration to integrate the new pieces of knowledge developed into the community.

Community management. Whatever the scope and the tools, a manager is essential for the proper functioning of the community. The community manager needs to cover three main tasks: 1) organize, 2) convey and catalyze, and 3) synthesize to integrate and value synchronous and asynchronous interactions.

User experience is about understanding the operational model of the community in terms of processes/practices, methods for organization and

⁴ Catana, G.C., Debremaeker, I., Szkola, S.S.E. and Williquet, F., The Communities of Practice Playbook, EUR 30466 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2021, ISBN 978-92-76-26344-9, doi:10.2760/42416, JRC122830.

tools. Different levels of satisfaction/concern with the workings of the community have to be identified.

Measurement constantly assesses the community's vitality and results through quantitative and qualitative methods.

Depending on the goals, activities and interactions needed, the tools for community engagement can vary accordingly. On the one side of the spectrum, the "convey mode" requires basic instruments, such as a mailing list and social media accounts. Some additional features may be needed to implement a community in "contribute mode", such as a platform to interact.

A further step is essential for "collaborate mode", which needs synchronous work (and possibly in-person activities). On the other side of the spectrum, "co-create mode" requires a combination of online and offline mechanisms and strong facilitation skills (online workshops, in-person dialogues, etc.) to facilitate working groups in producing new outcomes together.

3. COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT IN REINFORCING

A decade of experiments and practices in Europe on Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) and Open Science has created a vibrant community of actors, institutions and organizations of different nature (universities, research institutes, firms, CSOs, NGOs, R&I intermediaries and hybrid actors) that can bring their experience to the table. Establishing a productive space for dialogue will help collect best practices, tools and capacity-building pathways as well as identify gaps and blind spots and, thus, in general, define together ORRI processes that support the needs of organizations, institutions and territories willing to embark on for the first time or to enhance their ORRI experience.

For this reason, community engagement is a key asset in REINFORCING. REINFORCING has devoted a specific work package to community engagement activities (WP2), led by the Coordinator and in which most of the partners are involved both to mobilize sub-communities so as to design better tools and open calls and to receive feedback for their project activities finalization thanks to the community intelligence and contribution. Thus, this work package will activate not only the REINFORCING Consortium – which is constituted of experienced partners in ORRI monitoring, facilitation, implementation and evaluation of ORRI and thus in the best position to categorize ORRI resources but also to design new tools - but also ORRI community at large, including actors from key communities where the implementation of ORRI is still scattered - for instance, Open Innovation, Balkan area and Missions have been already identified as communities with which collaborate to co-design new tools and specific open calls. Throughout the project, active listening exercises will help collect inputs and feedback from actual enablers and implementers of ORRI practices.

WP2 sets a well-defined strategy to spark and maintain a continuous dialogue within the ORRI community at large in specific phases of the project duration. Further improvements and refinements will be integrated at critical checkpoints, and Community insights will also be considered. In any case, also other WPs (especially WP3 and WP6 but to some extent also WP1, WP4 and WP5) contribute to the community engagement set of activities.

3.1 REINFORCING: BETWEEN “COLLABORATE” AND “CO-CREATE” MODES

REINFORCING community engagement builds on the idea that knowledge and experience are distributed and that different actors (intended both as entities and as actors) hold different pieces of information and views that, when combined together, can draw a more complete picture of an issue and can provide more appropriate solutions to action⁵.

This is even more true for intricate topics, such as ORRI, which has constant evolutions and demands transformations at multiple levels, from policies and governance to institutions. This is the case for REINFORCING, which aims at bringing together a variety of actors with different levels of experience (both experienced stakeholders and entities that are new to ORRI issues and actions) and organisational nature.

Mainstreaming ORRI in different territorial and institutional settings requires complex considerations and strategies, which entail facilitated spaces for mobilizing collective intelligence, sharing reflections and experiences, and enabling transformational actions.

REINFORCING will embrace a hybrid participation mode, which will mainly comprise “collaborate” and “co-create” modes of engagement with the broad scope of enabling mutual learning and the co-design of useful and meaningful tools and resources with and for the ORRI community. “Convey” and “contribute” modes are also performed to inform and to get information, as a basis of the more interactive approaches.

3.2 REINFORCING COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT OPERATIONAL MODEL AND TOOLS

According to the hybrid participation mode, from collaboration to co-creation, here following the REINFORCING operational model:

⁵ https://media.nesta.org.uk/documents/Nesta_Playbook_001_Web.pdf

Vision. Mainstreaming the ORRI approach, leveraging on practical experiences of the community, is the leading principle of the ORRI community.

Governance and Leadership. The consortium has been constituted to represent a group of stakeholder leaders, especially in key ORRI sub-communities, and for this, they are able to mobilize their collective intelligence. Furthermore, all of them are well-integrated into pre-existing ORRI networks that can activate and solicitate. A continuous mapping exercise of new actors and entities to be included in the conversation is performed.

Convening. Partners involved in the WP2 actions are experienced entities in organizing, leading and facilitating online and offline conversations and dialogue, by engaging participants to co-evaluate or co-design tools of any kind that can be useful for the community.

Collaboration and cooperation. Co-designing meaningful resources for the ORRI community, and its sub-groups, is the main aim of the community engagement.

Community management. The management of the community is shared among different partners of the consortium in charge of the different community engagement actions and related tools. A shared strategy, led by the WP leader (FGB), is the basis of the engagement plan.

User experience and Measurement. A set of qualitative and quantitative methods to assess the efficacy of the actions will be set according to the tools usage.

To achieve its goals, REINFORCING combines mainly 4 different sets of tools for community engagement:

- Targeted communities workshops
- Workshops to support REINFORCING project activities
- Networking actions with other ORRI projects
- Dialogue with the international ORRI community

3.2.1 TARGETED COMMUNITIES WORKSHOPS

Research indicates that the implementation of RRI in H2020 lacked consistency and was susceptible to great variations depending on the geographical zones and/or fields of application. Therefore, REINFORCING

has made the conscious choice of adopting a community engagement that targets those specific communities and fields where the adoption of RRI has been low or uneven. The project connects its funding strategy (cascading grants) and the development of user-focused services with the engagement strategy towards specific, selected communities to guarantee the reduction of disparities within different territories across the ERA.

At the time of the proposal writing, three main stakeholder groups (communities) were identified as a priority: the Open Innovation community (subset of the private sector), the Balkans region and the participants in the EU Missions.

A broader set of participants will be identified through the gap analysis and dialogue with different communities - including during the international conference - and will also be specifically targeted.

For those communities, the project will develop a multilayered engagement process, mainly under WP2 but also with actions under WP3 and WP6, that will include different tools such as: targeted communication, online/in-person workshops, surveys, and interviews to gain a deeper understanding of their values and needs and to generate services and solutions to increase the institutionalization of useful, effective and user-centered ORRI practices leading to greater buy-in. Fair and equitable engagement for participants will be ensured through a needs assessment to adapt the process to their specific constraints.

The practical implementation of this active engagement includes a layered set of activities anchored around the calls for proposals for the cascading grants (both booster and incubators) and works in 3 layers: participatory activities to elicit needs, communication to expand the community base and trainings to sustain the engagement.

Before the launch of the calls:

- Identification and connection to the relevant players in the community and/or field through key partners (EBN, UNIVERSITY of Novi Sad, FGB, SD and ERRIN - advisory board member) to engage institutions and organizations (this will include putting the extended

REINFORCING network to work, leveraging existing EU and national initiatives).

- To kick-off the process, the consortium will organize online and face-to-face interactive workshops to gain a deeper understanding of the challenges, needs and constraints faced by these organizations.

While the call is open:

- Support from the Communication team to expand the reach to larger circles of the different communities, to widen the impact of the calls and to invite the communities to contribute and receive support from REINFORCING - through different tools and resources of the project.

During the implementation of the funded projects:

For those awarded funds

- Support and services throughout the implementation of their activities, training modules on ORRI principles and practices.
- Peer-learning activities, REINFORCING webinars. REINFORCING Impact Prizes
- Matchmaking services
- Mentoring services

For non-successful applicants

- Communication activities
- Trainings: crash courses (thematically oriented trainings about specific ORRI needs emerging from the interaction with the community) and clinics (solution-oriented modules relying on peer-to-peer learning on specific challenges faced by different target groups).
- Collaboration with sister projects

3.2.2 WORKSHOPS TO SUPPORT PROJECT ACTIVITIES

Building a central point of expertise on a wide and rapidly evolving issue such as ORRI requires careful attention, openness and responsiveness to the solicitations and stimuli coming from society. For this reason, all REINFORCING activities (and all project work packages) are permeated by

actions aimed at opening a dialogue with different societal actors explicitly or tacitly dealing with ORRI. These actions respond to the need of building interactive modes of engagement (i.e., “collaborate” and “co-create”) and will contribute to enlarge and reinforce the ORRI community, harness its collective intelligence and refining the project activities, which will be beneficial for the community itself.

In concrete terms REINFORCING consortium will organize four workshops under WP2 across different project work packages (WP1; WP3; WP5) to:

- Gather crowdsourced suggestions on the ORRI taxonomy, which will be at the heart of the organization of the REINFORCING platform.
- Cluster suggestions from the community to collectively shape the pathways that will help users navigate the resources available on the REINFORCING platform.
- Collect valuable insights from the ORRI community to be used for the development of REINFORCING policy recommendations (which will be collected during the project international conference in the second year of the project).
- Validate the final set of policy recommendations which will be produced in the fourth year of the project.

3.2.3 NETWORKING ACTIONS WITH OTHER ORRI PROJECTS

Community engagement is also supported by WP6, the work package aimed at raising awareness on ORRI benefits and maximizing exploitation, in particular in Task 6.3, devoted to “Networking and joint activities”. This work package has a strong focus on building alliances and joint activities with other projects funded under WIDERA.

With regard to projects, REINFORCING has the contractual obligation established by the European Commission to develop networking and communication activities to work with specific consortia. REINFORCING will foster regular collaboration (meetings every 6-8 months) with projects that have the same contractual dissemination obligation from the EC (ESC, IMPETUS, iRISE, OSIRIS and TIER2). The goal of this activity is to have regular exchanges among projects, sharing outcomes, experiences and

lessons learned, and at the same to joint efforts in the dissemination of results and resources.

One of the REINFORCING propositions is to release a collaborative Newsletter together with these projects every 4 months, reaching around 1000 people who will be regularly engaged in the project community. This collaborative approach to the Newsletter is aimed at triggering a snowball/networking effect and enabling the project to reach beyond its 'usual suspects' audience, therefore contributing to widening the REINFORCING community.

Beyond the preparation of collaborative Newsletters, REINFORCING will also develop case-by-case dissemination and outreach plans with single projects revolving around the topics addressed by the project's cascading grants.

Regarding other ORRI-related projects, REINFORCING partners will build *ad hoc* conversations around the specific topics at the center of REINFORCING cascading grants. In concrete terms, online webinars with invited speakers and interested actors will be organized to explore the topics of the REINFORCING calls (i.e., Open Innovation, EU Missions, Balkans + 4 more topics, which will be identified based on the evidence-based analysis run in WP1 and REINFORCING community feedback in WP2).

3.2.4 DIALOGUE WITH THE INTERNATIONAL ORRI COMMUNITY

The REINFORCING project aims to establish an extensive global network of ORRI actors and networks under a WP3 focused activity. It will also make use of existing EU networks in which consortium members are part of as partners, e.g. ROSiE, TechEthos, SuperMoRRI, ENRICH Global, Virtual Institute of Responsible Innovation, the Knowledge Valorisation Community of Practice etc.). This network is envisioned to span across four continents, encompassing Europe, Africa, the Americas, and the Asia-Pacific region. Its primary objectives are as follows:

- Facilitating Ongoing Exchange: the network will serve as a platform for fostering a continuous exchange of knowledge, experiences, and advancements related to ORRI. This exchange will be a recurring

feature, with regular meetings starting from the first months of 2024. These meetings will bring together experts, practitioners, and stakeholders from various regions to share insights and progress in the field.

- **Contributing to the One-Stop Source:** the network will play a pivotal role in enriching the One-Stop Source platform by providing valuable contributions, such as best practices, innovative tools, and real-world experiences. This collaborative effort will enhance the quality and comprehensiveness of the resource, making it a valuable reference for the RRI community.
- **Multiplying the Project's Impact:** in conjunction with WP6, the network will function as a multiplier, amplifying the reach and impact of the project's outcomes on a global scale. By leveraging the collective expertise and connections within the network, the project aims to make a significant and lasting impact on the promotion and adoption of ORRI principles worldwide.

After identifying challenges and establishing a sense of community and belonging among network members, the project will shift its focus towards developing a sustainability plan for the network. This plan will ensure the network's longevity and continued effectiveness beyond the project's duration.

Furthermore, there will be a face-to-face meeting of the network, coinciding with the REINFORCING international conference scheduled in M22. This in-person gathering will provide an invaluable opportunity for network members to engage in face-to-face discussions, deepen collaborations, and further strengthen the global RRI community.

4. “CONVEY” AND “CONTRIBUTE” ACTIONS TO MOBILIZE FURTHER COMMUNITIES

Beyond a more engaging set of activities, described in Section 3, further actions to inform and inspire as well as collect feedback have been foreseen in REINFORCING.

4.1 SOCIAL MEDIA (X, LinkedIn, YouTube)

Social media is an integral part of the management of the REINFORCING community(ies), relying on past successful experiences. Although levels of participation will differ from one platform to another, social media will be very useful especially in the case of the “convey” and “contributes” modes of engagement, namely through sharing information and inspiring the users (one-way communication) and enabling feedback from the community (two-way communication).

REINFORCING has selected 3 main social media channels which are the most suitable ones for the project’s objectives. REINFORCING will take advantage of existing social media channels with a well-established ORRI community behind them.

Partners will coordinate and activate their own social media and networks to echo REINFORCING actions, maximizing outreach, visibility of the project, and community engagement efforts.

Depending on target, scope, type and level of interaction needed, three main social media will be used:

- **X**

REINFORCING inherited and renamed the X (ex-Twitter) account of the TRANSFORM project, which was funded under Horizon 2020 (Swafs-14 on territorial RRI) and already engages a wide ORRI community.

REINFORCING will monitor the evolution of this social media channel and, if necessary, will study the possibility of moving its activities to other channels that fulfil the same objectives, such as Threads or Bluesky.

- **LinkedIn**

REINFORCING also inherited and renamed the TRANSFORM project LinkedIn group, which brought together EU-funded projects and relevant initiatives and key stakeholders working on ORRI to create a space to exchange and share knowledge, experience and lessons learned, exploring synergies and fostering networking.

- YouTube

A YouTube account will be set up to host videos created within the project (i.e., Dissemination project videos) and events (conferences, webinars, etc.) organized and recorded in the project framework.

4.2 ORRI AMBASSADORS AND FACILITATORS

One of the objectives of REINFORCING is to serve as a central point of expertise, catalyzing ORRI-related collaborations among different actors. Taking stock from partners' experience and building on the literature review and analysis conducted under WP1, the project aims at valuing and systematizing ORRI expertise by drawing a virtual map of ORRI Ambassadors (entities which have hands-on experiences of ORRI implementation in their own institution and territory) and ORRI Facilitators (i.e. entities with strong experience in supporting and facilitating ORRI institutional changes).

The map will be available on the REINFORCING website and platform and will become a point of reference for the platform's users (i.e., helping potential ORRI enablers to connect with local experts, matching their need for specific competences).

4.3 REINFORCING CALLS EVALUATORS

One of the objectives of REINFORCING is to provide financial support for institutional and territorial transformations. To achieve this the project will award 96 grants designed to boost institutions scaling up their ORRI experience as well as to incubate newcomer territories experimenting with ORRI for the first time. Evaluators play a central role in this process. They are external experts selected to ensure that the evaluation process is both

rigorous and impartial. They will evaluate the projects already shortlisted by the consortium that will be awarded for financial support. The project comprises four ORRI Booster calls and three ORRI Incubator calls and each call will have a consortium-selected panel of three evaluators, resulting in a total of 21 evaluators.

Evaluators in the REINFORCING community will bring both active and passive contributions. As a matter of fact, evaluators will have significant expertise in RRI and will be well-connected within relevant networks. They will actively promote calls for proposals and project resources, acting as key advocates. They could also take a more passive role and be a part of the broader community, using their expertise and networks to support REINFORCING initiatives. In both active and passive roles, evaluators play a crucial part in advancing the community's goals.

4.4 ORRI PROJECTS AND INITIATIVES INTERVIEWED UNDER WP1

The creation and nurturing of the REINFORCING community will also build on the activities run in WP1, the project work package aimed at consolidating evidence-based knowledge on ORRI. One of the objectives of WP1 is to systematically review previous and ongoing ORRI initiatives, relying on existing resources available on the RRI Tools platform, Cordis and open repositories like Zenodo. Thanks to this extensive mapping of ORRI initiatives, a key group of ORRI actors will be identified, and some of them also be interviewed in order to refine an ORRI taxonomy to be used to organize the REINFORCING platform.

Actors and initiatives that both explicitly and tacitly worked or are working on ORRI will be considered and will be invited to actively contribute to the REINFORCING community both under their involvement in WP1 actions and in WP2-led activities.

5. ETHICAL MEASURES TO BE ADDRESSED

Potential ethical issues connected to community engagement activities will be monitored and properly handled by REINFORCING partners. Regarding personal data, an informed consent form (see Annex I) will be used in order to handle personal data in compliance with the GDPR.

ANNEX I

Informed Consent for participation in community engagement activities in the REINFORCING project

Key information

Project Name	<i>Responsible tEerritories and Institutions eNable and Foster Open Research and inClusive Innovation for traNsitions Governance (REINFORCING)</i>
Coordinator	Fondazione Gianni Bassetti (FGB), Italy
Funder	European Commission, Horizon Europe Framework Programme (Call topic: HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01-40)
Duration	50 months, from January 2023 to February 2027
Website	reinforcing.eu

Description of the Project

REINFORCING supports organizations and institutions in Europe to transition to a new paradigm where responsibility and openness drive research and innovation processes. In order to do that, the project will offer a single-entry point to the support services your organization needs for its transformation. The REINFORCING one-stop source provide:

1. Tested resources to guide EU entities towards more responsible and inclusive research and innovation practices. Project partners will curate and organize them in different pathways to help users navigate the change.
 2. A tailored set of services, including training modules, to build capacity and assist with the appropriate support during ORRI practice.
 3. 7 open calls to financially support experiments and pilots in ORRI, both if organizations are newcomers wishing to embark on ORRI and if they are experienced entities that would like to strengthen ORRI implementation.
- All these activities will rely on the strong experience of the project partners and will contribute to reinforcing the ORRI community and impacts.

Name and contact details of the data controller

Fondazione Giannino Bassetti,
Project Coordinator and WP2 leader - Co-designing guidance with and for
the community
Via Barozzi, 4
20122, Milano, Italy
Phone: +39 02 781933
Email: info@fondazionebassetti.org

Kind of Data collected

During the REINFORCING community engagement activities personal data could be collected. This could include: your name, contact information (email, phone number), occupation, professional background, and your personal opinions.

No sensitive personal data (e.g. health, ethnicity, political opinion, religious or philosophical conviction) is collected within the project.

Furthermore, photos, videoconferences screenshots, as well as audio and video recordings, note-taking, collection of written information through post-its and alike can be performed in the community engagement activities of REINFORCING.

Participation in the community

Participation in the community of REINFORCING can vary depending on the participants' needs and roles. It could be engagement in online and off-line exchanges, including on-site workshops, online trainings, webinars, online meetings and social media conversations

Participation in the activities is always voluntary: you may choose not to respond to any question or to discuss a particular topic, and you can terminate your participation at any time. If you decide to end your participation, it will not be possible to remove contributions that you have shared before opting out.

Usage of your Data

The data generated within the community engagement activities (workshops/conferences/social media interactions, etc.) will be used within the framework of REINFORCING. This includes the co-design of services and tools to support ORRI actors in implementing ORRI actions.

The data generated can also be analysed and used for scientific publications on ORRI, for dissemination activities in the project timeframe as well as reporting on project progress to the European Commission. This includes deliverables, publications, reports, policy briefs, web pages and social media.

Storing of your Data

Your data will be stored in a safe EU-based server (Google Drive), fully GDPR compliant. Due to requirements of the European Commission, the data collected might be stored until up to five years after the end of the project (meaning December 2031).

Anonymised data might become part of publications (including scientific papers), project reports and other dissemination materials.

Personal data will be made publicly available only if agreed with individuals included in the dataset and if public availability can be justified by project purposes.

Your data will not be sent to third parties. The sole purpose of storing your data falls within the purposes of REINFORCING, including dissemination and policy support.

Code of Conduct

Participation in REINFORCING is meant to be as agreeable and pleasant as possible for all those involved. Therefore, all participants agree to respect the following rules:

- Racism and discrimination: racist comments, discrimination on the basis of sex, age, or disability, publication of racist or sexist pictures and insulting persons are strictly banned.
- REINFORCING may not be misused for political, religious or advertising purposes.
- Infringements of copyright laws are not permitted.

- All participants' conduct should always be appropriate and never offensive or deprecating.

Consent

After having stated these general conditions and rules, we are looking forward to a good cooperation and positive project results. We would like to thank you in advance for your participation in the project.

The undersigned declare that they understand and consent to the conditions and rules of REINFORCING, receiving a copy of this declaration of consent.

Location, day/month/year

Participant's signature